

RESPONSE TO EC CONSULTATION ON DRAFT EU DPP REGISTRY IMPLEMENTING REGULATION

Publication date	May 27, 2026
Version	1
Contributors	CIRPASS-2 consortium
Abstract	This document contains the responses by CIRPASS-2 consortium partners to the EC consultation on the draft EU DPP Registry Implementing Regulation.
Citation	CIRPASS-2 consortium. (2026). Response to EC consultation on Draft EU DPP Registry Implementing Regulation. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20417510

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
1.0	May 27, 2026	Final V1	

CIRPASS-2 CONSORTIUM

#	Participant Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
1	Commissariat A L'Energie Atomique Et Aux Energies Alternatives	CEA	France
2	Tallinna Tehnikaülikool	TALTECH	Estonia
3	Mindworks Industries Ou	MWX	Estonia
4	DIGITALEUROPE AISBL	DIGITALEUROPE	Belgium
5	E CIRCULAR APS	E CIRCULAR APS	Denmark
6	F6S Network Ireland Limited	F6S IE	Ireland
7	Global Textile Scheme GmbH	GTS	Germany
8	maki Consulting GmbH	MAKI	Germany
9	Ekodenge Muhendislik Mimarlik Danismanlik Ticaret Anonim Sirketi	EKODENGE	Sweden
10	Stiftelsen Chalmers Industriteknik	CIT	Sweden
11	Nederlandse Organisatie Voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek TNO	TNO	Netherlands
12	BIO Innovation Service SAS	BIOIS	France
13	Technische Universiteit DELFT	TU Delft	Netherlands
14	Asociacion De Empresas Tecnologicas INNOVALIA	INNOVALIA	Spain
15	CBT Comunicacion & Multimedia SL	CBT	Spain
16	Asociacion Para Desarrollo De La Economia Del Dato	BAIDATA	Spain
17	GS1 In Europe	GS1 IN EUROPE	Belgium
18	AOC Innovation	AOC INNOVATION	France
19	+IMPAKT Luxembourg SARL	+IMPAKT	Luxembourg
20	Industrie 4.0 Osterreich - Die Plattform Fur Intelligente Produktion	PIA	Austria
21	FUJITSU Technology Solutions	FJBE	Belgium
22	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Forderung Der Angewandten Forschung EV	Fraunhofer	Germany
23	Extra Red SRL	EXTRA RED SRL	Italy
24	European Apparel And Textile Confederation Aisbl	EURATEX	Belgium
25	IOXIO OY	IOXIO OY	Finland
26	Suomen Tekstiili Ja Muoti Ry	FINATEX	Finland
27	KEZZLER AS	Kezzler	Norway
28	EON Cloud Technology KFT	EON	Hungary
29	Avery Dennison Atma GmbH	atma.io	Austria
30	Circular.Fashion UG	circ.fashion	Germany
31	TRIPLER	TripleR	Belgium

32	SCANTRUST BV	SCANTRUST BV	Netherlands
33	ARCELIK A.S.	ARCELIK	Türkiye
34	WHATT.IO AB	whatt.io	Sweden
35	Gorenje Gospodinjski Aparati DOO	GORENJE	Slovenia
36	Hisense Gorenje Europe Poslovne Storitve DOO	HGE	Slovenia
37	Manufacture Francaise Des Pneumatiques MICHELIN	MICHELIN	France
38	COBUILDER AS	COBUILDER	Norway
39	DIN Deutsches Institut Fuer Normung EV	DIN e.V.	Germany
40	VDE Verband Der Elektrotechnik Elektronik Informationstechnik EV	VDE	Germany
41	Energy Web AG	Energy Web AG	Switzerland
42	WORLDLINE France	WORLDLINE FR	France
43	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt	PTB	Germany
44	Digital Data Chain Consortium GbR	DDCC	Germany
45	ZVEI e. V.	ZVEI e.V.	Germany
46	Association of Service and Computer Dealers International	ASCDI	US
47	Open Blockchain for Asset Disposition Alliance (OBADA)	OBADA	US
48	Green Electronics Council	GEC	US
49	Textile Exchange	TextileExchange	US
50	IPoint Systems GmbH	IPoint	Germany

Grant Agreement No.: 101158775
Call: DIGITAL-2023-CLOUD-DATA-04
Topic: DIGITAL-2023-CLOUD-DATA-04-DIGIPASS
Type of action: DIGITAL Simple Grants

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

© CIRPASS-2 Consortium, 2024-2027

Except otherwise noted, original content on this document is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence. This licence enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator. The licence allows for commercial use.

The CIRPASS-2 consortium appreciates the opportunity to be able to provide feedback in the European Commission consultation on the DPP Registry Implementing Regulation. We particularly welcome the adoption of strong semantic interoperability capabilities by the DPP Registry. To further improve and future-proof this text, we believe that the following changes should be implemented, and suggest alternative formulations as well as justification for each change.

→ **Article 1.2(d)** “*the process of registering and storing unique identifiers;*” Unfortunately, the entire text of this draft regulation reproduces the confusion introduced in prEN 18219 by CEN/CENELEC JTC-24 and in which no clear distinction is made between the unique product identifier and the “web link enabled by” the unique product identifier, a distinction that is fortunately very clear in the ESPR¹. This is a major problem as this creates both conceptual confusion² and introduces risk of implementation errors and inconsistent interpretation. **Suggested replacement for Article 1.2(d)** “*the process of registering and storing unique identifiers, including the unique product identifier, a web link enabled by the unique product identifier and a link to the back-up hosted by a digital product passport service provider ;*”

→ **Article 1.2(e) Recital 3** - Clarification could be beneficial regarding how customs-related integration and authority access are expected to function for EEA countries that participate in the internal market but are not part of the EU Customs Union. In particular, clarification regarding operational interaction models for non-EU customs authorities may improve predictability for implementation and interoperability planning.

→ **Article 1.2 (g)** “*statuses related to registered digital product passport data;*” The wording here does not make clear which statuses a “registered digital product passport data” goes through and if the related DPP data has its own separate status.

→ **Article 2(2)** “...that enables a user to verify its identity in order to authenticate themselves in the registry;” The distinction between natural persons and legal person is not clear in this definition, although the distinction is relevant for several articles (such as the protection of personal data)

→ **Article 3(c)** “*a verification platform to confirm and verify the existence and completeness of the digital product passports;*” This article mentions the verification of the “existence and completeness of the DPP” whereas Article 8 6(a) mentions only the verification of the “existence ... of mandatory data to be uploaded in the registry.” Therefore, the requirements for “existence” and “completeness” should be clarified. Furthermore, the verification of ‘existence’ of the web link enabled by the unique product identifier should be clarified as this might mean simply verifying that the link has been provided during the registration process or verifying that the link points to a live DPP data server (i.e. the link is not ‘stale’).³

→ **Article 3(f)** “*a list of the digital product passport service providers;*” In alignment with Recital (3), **suggested replacement for Article 3(f)** “*a list of the **backup** digital product passport service providers;*” The text should clarify the list’s operational purpose and how it contributes to the functioning of the registry and of the European DPP system in general. It should further be clarified what information would be contained in this list, the obligations a DPP service provider would have to fulfil in order to be added to that

¹ Article 2 (30) ‘*unique product identifier*’ means a unique string of characters for the identification of a product that also enables a web link to the digital product passport;

² The unique product identifier identifies the **product**, whereas the web link it enables identifies the **Web location** that should be queried to retrieve information about the product. For the same unique product identifier, there could possibly be multiple associated web links, either to retrieve different information about the product, or simply because it is convenient to provide different links that resolve to the same Web location. Of course, some of the unique product identification schemes defined in prEN18219 already come in the form of Web links, in which case, the economic operator resorting to those schemes chooses to reject the previously cited possibilities. At least one Web link enabled by the unique product identifier should be registered in the EU DPP Registry, along with the unique product identifier.

³ A verification by the Registry of the status of the link during the registration process could provide assurances to all actors required by law to make the link available to consumers before purchase (retail, eCommerce, online marketplaces, etc.)

list, whether this list is static or dynamic, how it is maintained and updated, and if a DPP service provider would have the right and a method to request a list of registered DPP backup (or primary) links which are claimed to be hosted by them.

→ **Articles 4 and 5** – These articles introduce strong dependencies on eIDAS-compatible trust services, qualified electronic signatures, electronic seals and electronic attestations of attributes for both economic operators and other value chain actors. Additional clarification regarding interoperability expectations for EEA actors and systems could support smoother onboarding and implementation, particularly in situations where relevant EU legal frameworks are still in the process of EEA incorporation.

→ **Article 4(4)** “Economic operators shall retain the status as verified economic operators until their electronic identification means expire but [...]”: It should be clarified whether the verified status of an economic operator can be revoked, either by competent authorities or upon cessation of activities. Furthermore, the relationship between the validity of a digital product passport (final sentence of article 4(4)) and the verification status of the economic operator requires clarification as it is unclear why the validity status of a correctly registered DPP should automatically change (and possibly even be revoked) after 3 years.

→ **Article 7** – This article assumes a Member State-based operational model through the designation of a single national administrator responsible for managing registry access rights. Additional clarification could be beneficial regarding how this model is expected to operate for EEA countries participating in the DPP ecosystem through the EEA framework rather than through EU membership.

→ **Article 8.1** “For products referred to in Article 1(1), point (a), a digital product passport shall be registered by economic operator placing the product on the market or putting it into service at least at the level specified in the applicable delegated acts (model, batch or item level)...” We welcome the flexibility offered by this feature, but an economic operator (EO) should not be required to register millions of voluntary item level DPPs, if each of them includes a reference to the DPP at the (batch or model) mandatory level. This adds cost to both EO and the Registry with minimal apparent value.

→ **Article 8.3 and 4.** “Where the digital product passport is created at item level, in accordance with paragraph 1, both batch and model identifiers shall be linked to that digital product passport where batch and model design exist in the production.” The ‘linking’ mechanism should be briefly described. This might be performed by adding this information (model and batch identifiers) into the DPP Registry or alternatively, by including it amongst the mandatory DPP information that will be defined by delegated acts.

→ **Article 8.6(b)** “Upon submission for registration, the Commission shall automatically verify: ... the conformity of the digital product passport with the granularity level (model, batch or item)” It is unclear what will be verified. This might be performed by requiring the submission of DPP granularity information during the registration process and verifying this information or performed by an automatic retrieval and verification by the DPP Registry of the entire DPP data using the web link enabled by the unique product identifier.

→ **Article 8.6(d)** “Upon submission for registration, the Commission shall automatically verify: ... where relevant, the link to the back-up hosted by a digital product passport service provider;” It is unclear what will be verified. This might consist of verifying that a web link has been provided during the registration process or a more elaborate automatic check by the DPP Registry to verify that the web link provided indeed returns conformant DPP data.

→ **Article 8.6(e)** “Upon submission for registration, the Commission shall automatically verify: ... the use of a qualified electronic signature or a qualified electronic seal in accordance with Regulation (EU) No 910/2014.” **Suggested replacement for Article 8.6(e)** “the use of a qualified electronic signature or a qualified electronic seal **for the registration submission request**, in accordance with Regulation (EU) No 910/2014.” The proposed clarification makes it clear that it is the registration submission data that is sealed, not the DPP data.

→ **Article 8.8(d)** “Additionally, the Commission shall store in the registry the following information as part of the registration data: ... (d) registrant information, including date and time of the registration and the integrity of the digital product passport as part of the evidence of the registration event.” Clarification is required on the integrity information that will be stored. This could be interpreted to mean integrity of the registration

data or integrity of the DPP data itself, which would require an automatic retrieval and hash code calculation by the DPP Registry of the DPP data retrieved using the web link enabled by the unique product identifier.

→ **Article 8.8(d)** “Additionally, the Commission shall store in the registry the following information as part of the registration data: [...]” Should the location (the web link enabled by the unique product identifier) of the DPP itself not be registered?

→ **Article 9.2** Proof of registration could additionally contain the web link enabled by the unique product identifier and that has been submitted during the registration process. This would support all in-person retailers and online dealers in providing ‘validated’ DPP links to consumers. Indeed, this would provide them with the confidence that the links to DPPs for products they are offering on the market and provided by economic operators are indeed those that were registered in the DPP Registry.⁴

→ **Article 9.3.** “Proof of registration shall be guaranteed by means of a qualified electronic seal as provided for in Article 38 of Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and by means of a qualified timestamp as provided for in Article 42 of that Regulation.” **Suggested replacement for Article 9.3** “Proof of registration shall be guaranteed by means of a qualified electronic seal as provided for in Article 38 of Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and by means of a qualified timestamp as provided for in Article 42 of that Regulation **or in the form of an electronic attestation of attributes.**” Adding this second possibility opens the (future) possibility to automatically revoke the registration credential as a follow-up consequence of market withdrawal decisions by market surveillance authorities. This would allow the revocation information to be automatically transferred to any party making use of the registration credential for their own compliance needs (e.g. retailers, eCommerce and online marketplaces). This would simplify and accelerate the withdrawal of unsafe products from the market.

→ **Article 10.2** The meaning of “digital product passport version” is not defined in this document, making it unclear what is meant by “linking” to “each new digital product passport version”. It is generally expected that, if corrections are made in a DPP, the web link pointing to it will not change as it is typically (e.g. for QR codes or NFC tags) encoded in the data carrier placed on the product. Versioning support by the DPP Registry to monitor changes to DPP data (if this is the objective of this clause) might require automatic retrieval and hash code generation over the DPP data. This may be both impractical and costly for product categories with dynamic or frequently updated attributes (as opposed to corrections of static attributes).

→ **Article 12.2(a)** The terms “typed” and “resolvable” in the context of ‘links between digital product passports’ are not defined.

→ **Article 12(3)** The article states metadata “shall be in conformity with the DCAT-AP specifications” — but DCAT-AP is a broad standard designed for data portals and catalogs. It is not specified whether this means the semantic repository will expose a full DCAT-AP catalog endpoint (machine-readable, queryable), or simply that the metadata fields of data models should map to DCAT-AP properties. The requirements should be clarified.

→ **Article 15** The absence of fallback mechanisms during registry downtime may create significant operational challenges for high-throughput economic operators, especially considering that the DPP Registry may be needed by the DPP Web Portal to retrieve the link to the backup DPP copy. Alternative registration options should be considered.

→ **Article 22** – This article refers to Member States being responsible for national interconnections and components used to access the registry. Clarification could be useful regarding how these responsibilities are expected to apply to EEA countries participating in the DPP Registry ecosystem, particularly in relation to customs integration, authority access management and national interoperability infrastructure.

⁴ The link validation process could additionally include a verification that the link points to a live server, that the server can serve DPP data, etc.

DISCLAIMER

The information provided in this presentation is for information purposes only. The CIRPASS-2 consortium partners are not responsible for any damage that could result from making use of this information.

Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, European Commission, or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union, the European Commission nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and should not be interpreted as reflecting those of CEN/CENELEC JTC 24.